

Preliminary test on the Modena Automotive Smart Area Backbone

Carlo Augusto Grazia, Salvatore Iandolo, Martin Klapez, and Maurizio Casoni

Abstract—The network infrastructure is a key factor for Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). Only reliable networking support can enable the low latency required by ITS for safety-related applications, where effectiveness, reliability, and timeliness play crucial roles. These characteristics are required to reach autonomous driving and, tailored for a living lab, are required to test it and design novel applications for connected vehicles and, generally speaking, enhance road safety. This paper introduces a test campaign performed to stress the Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA) backbone to efficiently evaluate the performance of the network infrastructure before starting the deployment of ITS services, including the installation of smart cameras and Road-Side Units (RSUs). The suite of tests has been designed to accommodate the automotive requirements, with the goal of evaluating the network latency in uncongested and congested situations, including the presence of QoS requirements. The results show that the MASA network is suitable for safety-related applications, introducing less than 100ms of induced latency in severe congested events for all the tested spots. This result is achievable thanks to the backbone characteristics and the partnership with the municipality that shares the physical network with the university, avoiding IST black boxes.

Index Terms—Autonomous Driving, Field Trials, LivingLab, MASA, V2X

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) has underscored the need for robust and reliable network infrastructures capable of supporting the stringent requirements of autonomous driving and safety-related applications. As cities evolve into smart environments, the network backbone must efficiently handle varying traffic loads while maintaining low latency and high reliability. The Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA¹), located in the heart of Italy’s motor valley, represents a pioneering initiative aimed at enhancing urban mobility through advanced network technologies.

This paper presents a comprehensive test campaign conducted to evaluate the performance of the MASA backbone under different network conditions. By examining network latency in both uncongested and congested scenarios, and considering Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, we aim to

determine the suitability of the MASA network for supporting ITS services. This includes the deployment of smart cameras and Road-Side Units (RSUs), which are critical for real-time applications such as autonomous driving and traffic management.

The evaluation leverages the Flexible Network Tester (Flent) [1] to simulate various traffic conditions and measure the network’s response. The tests focus on key performance indicators, including induced latency and traffic fairness among multiple flows. The findings from this study provide valuable insights into the capabilities of the MASA backbone and its readiness for future ITS deployments.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly overviews related works. Section III introduces the test methodology. Section IV describes the equipment utilized, its configuration, and Flent. Section V presents and analyzes the results while Section VI concludes the article.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several studies have addressed the challenges of network traffic management and QoS provisioning in urban environments. Traditional approaches often focus on ISP-centric strategies, such as FIFO queues and bandwidth throttling, aimed at controlling traffic flow and ensuring fair resource allocation. While effective to some extent, these methods often fall short in delivering consistently high performance, especially in congested scenarios [2], [3].

Researchers have explored various QoS differentiation techniques to prioritize critical traffic over less important data. Techniques like Differentiated Services (DiffServ) and Traffic Classifiers have been introduced to classify and prioritize packets based on their characteristics [4]. However, these techniques still rely on ISP-centric control and may not fully address the challenges posed by emerging applications and services, such as autonomous vehicles and smart city infrastructure.

The communication network infrastructure of a city must support the reliable and low-latency transmission required by autonomous systems and safety-critical applications. Studies have proposed innovative approaches to traffic management that focus on local bottleneck strategies. For instance, one approach suggests introducing controlled congestion points within the network to improve traffic handling and QoS differentiation. This method is particularly valuable in scenarios where ISP-centric traffic shaping struggles to meet the demands of diverse applications [5].

In the context of autonomous vehicles, real-time data transmission is crucial for vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communi-

C.A. Grazia, S. Iandolo, M. Klapez, and M. Casoni are with the Department of Engineering *Enzo Ferrari*, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, via Pietro Vivarelli, 10, 41125, Modena, Italy (e-mail: {carloaugusto.grazia, salvatore.iandolo, martin.klapez, maurizio.casoni}@unimore.it).

This study was carried out within the MOST – Sustainable Mobility National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1033 17/06/2022, CN00000023). This manuscript reflects only the authors’ views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

¹<https://www.automotivesmartarea.it>

Fig. 1: MASA & Tested Spots.

MASA Spot ID	Network Owner	Test hours
RSUc ₁	Municipality	2
RSUc ₂	Municipality	2
RSUa	Achanto	3

TABLE I: Summary of MASA networks tested.

Research by He et al. [6] explores routing optimization using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to dynamically change routing strategies and reallocate resources upon detecting congestion points. This approach is beneficial in multi-user mobile edge computing (MEC) networks, where efficient allocation of computational resources is critical.

Adaptive techniques at the application level also play a significant role in managing network congestion and ensuring QoS for safety-related applications. Video streaming applications, for example, often implement adaptive queue management (AQM) to adjust transmission rates and end-to-end parameters like chunk sizes. These adjustments help maintain performance even when ISP-deployed queuing disciplines are not optimal [7]. Kua et al. [8], [7] have extensively studied the impact of AQM on DASH-based content delivery, highlighting the benefits of adaptive techniques in maintaining QoS under varying network conditions.

Another important aspect is the Quality of Experience (QoE) for end-users. Jiang et al. [9] proposed the Q-FDBA framework, which enhances QoE fairness for video streaming by shaping and pacing traffic to avoid ISP bottleneck management. This approach demonstrates the potential of application-level adaptations in improving overall network performance

Fig. 2: Raspberry Pi 4 Model B as the testbed device.

and user satisfaction.

In smart city environments, the network backbone must support a wide range of applications, from autonomous transportation to emergency response systems. Xue et al. [10] introduced an intelligent and decentralized content diffusion system in smart-router networks, which enhances the efficiency and reliability of data transmission in urban settings. This system leverages the distributed nature of smart routers to optimize data flow and reduce latency, critical for real-time applications in smart cities.

Furthermore, Kumar et al. [11] discussed semi-oblivious traffic engineering, which aims to improve traffic management by considering both current network conditions and future demands. This approach helps in preemptively managing

Fig. 3: Overview of MASA network.

Fig. 4: Methodology for Flent tests.

congestion and ensuring consistent performance across the network.

This paper shows a preliminary test that does not take into account possible optimization based on our previous research on TCP Small Queues [12], TCP parallelization [13] and SDN [14], [15].

III. METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the MASA backbone performance, we conducted preliminary experiments on three different MASA spots representing the two possible fiber provider available in the city-center: one is the fiber owned by the municipality, while the other is provided by a third-part company Acantho. The topology that represent the MASA network is depicted in Figure 3. A key characteristic of MASA is the absence of ISPs, indeed the network can be summarized in the two main blocks of “access network” and “internet” (backbone). We locate the server processing the network data of our test in the shared municipality/university private network, and so there are no extra hops during tests. While Figure 3b show the case in which a connected vehicle is connected to the MASA smart nodes, we refer to Figure 3b in our tests. All tests adhered to this topology and the goal is to isolate the latency contribution of the backbone part, with emphasis on the induced latency in case of network congestion, stressing also fairness among multiple flows and QoS.

In total, the three tested spots have produced more than 7 hours of testing. We compiled all data, logs, and post-processed results into a repository [16]; the characteristics of the three spots are detailed in Table I, while the spots

position in the MASA field is available in Figure 1. Our testbed includes a Device Under Test (DUT), a Raspberry Pi Model 4 (RP4) with 8GB of RAM, and a 1 Gbit Ethernet interface, as shown in Figure 2. The RP4 runs Ubuntu-Server Linux and serves as the end-node device in the network configuration depicted on the left side of Figure 3 (Figure 3a). A desktop Arch-Linux node at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia hosted the server side of our tests, connected to the Internet via fiber without an ISP intermediary, as said. The end-to-end measured performance gives a snapshot of the bounds introduced by the infrastructure; indeed, since we connect the DUT to the Municipality’s cabinets, the measured performance corresponds to the network depicted in Figure 3b, without the contribution of the final access network (typically DSRC, with low-latency and low-bandwidth characteristics). Our tests aim to stress the core network of the living lab, forcing a high volume of traffic and examining the latency performance, in particular.

IV. FIELD SETUP AND FLENT

Our experiment are configured using the tool named Flent [1] (FLExible Network Tester) for performing the main tests, which have the following characteristics:

- 1) Four suites of flow transmissions between the RP4 and the server, as shown in Figure 4. These included a bulk upload, a bulk download, and two Real-time Response Under Load (RRUL) test variants. Details of these tests will be described later.
- 2) Two TCP variant configurations: TCP Cubic [17] and TCP BBR [18]. TCP Cubic is a widely used loss-based variant, while TCP BBR, a model-based variant by Google, significantly reduces queue occupancy at the bottleneck stage.

All tests ran three instances of the test family depicted in Figure 4, stressing the network in various ways:

- **Bulk Download.** A TCP download from the server to the DUT, in parallel with an ICMP flow. The test lasts 30 seconds: 5 seconds of ICMP alone, 20 seconds with both ICMP and TCP, and 5 final seconds of ICMP alone. This captures the network’s response to a single congesting TCP download and identifies potential misbehavior due to lack of queue management.

Fig. 5: Thr and ping combined.

Fig. 6: Thr and ping over time.

Fig. 7: RRUL BE 1.

Fig. 8: RRUL BE 2.

Fig. 9: RRUL QoS.

- **Bulk Upload.** A TCP upload from the DUT to the server, in parallel with an ICMP flow. Similar in segmentation to the previous test, it also captures the TCP RTT since flow control is managed by the DUT.
- **Real-Time Response Under Load (RRUL) Best-Effort.** Four TCP flows in both upload and download, together with four UDP flows and an ICMP flow, create severe congestion, stressing the network with multiple flows of equal priority. This tests for the presence of a packet scheduling algorithm and its effectiveness in equal treatment of flows.
- **RRUL QoS version.** Identical to the previous test, but with four TCP flows (both download and upload) marked according to four different traffic classes: CS5, EF, BE, and BK (highest to lowest priority), representing real-time, expedited forwarding, best-effort, and background

traffic, respectively.

V. TEST RESULTS

Almost all our plots report candlesticks, the bottom and top sticks represent the 1th and 99th percentiles, while the bottom and top of the middle box the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The central line represent the median (i.e. 50th percentile), while crosses indicates the statistical outliers.

The results of a single bulk stream are depicted in Figures 5 and 6. At first look, the two spots named RSUc1 and RSUc2 perform very closely, while RSUa manifests a very different throughput both in download (Figure 5a) and upload (Figure 5b), which also corresponds to lower download latency. It is important to notice that these initial values do not compromise the RSUa spot evaluation. Indeed, an RSU installed on that network would generate an amount of traffic that is still lower than the bottleneck triggered during this test, close to 50Mbps in download and 10Mbps in upload, respectively. The time series view, available in Figure 6, shows the impact of the TCP download on the orange ping latency, which is higher and more unstable for RSUc1 rather than RSUa. A throughput of 50Mbps, stable, with less than 15ms of latency (Figure 6b), is better than a 700Mbps throughput with 40ms of latency (Figure 6a): this is true for safety-related applications where timeliness is essential, while, for applications like the bulk download of stream-videos for backup purposes, higher throughput is preferred since latency does not impact a non-real-time application severely. This information is good to be collected in advance, before the deployment of RSUs, since both the applications and scenarios, with their well-different parameters, metrics, and constraints, belong to the MASA living lab.

Continuing, results for the RRUL Best Effort version are available in Figures 7 and 8. Starting with Figure 7a, it is again notable how RSUa performs badly from a pure bandwidth point of view, with lower download and upload values concerning RSUc1 and RSUc2. At the same time, in a congested environment, the latency gap is between three and five times higher moving from RSUa to RSUc1 and RSUc2. Figure 7b, instead, reports the throughput of the four TCP downloads during the test; this tells us that RSUc2 does not schedule the different flows, with the flow BE4

reaching higher throughput with respect to the other three. This information is confirmed by Figure 8a also, with UDP BE2 that registered lower latency with respect to the other UDP flows and the ICMP PING result close to values of 60ms. A different behavior is reported for RSUC1; comparing Figure 8a with Figure 8b, the latency values change for RSUC1 moving from 20ms of average latency for UDP and ICMP traffic, while the TPC RTT of the four flows is close to 40ms. Such a pattern happens when a packet scheduler isolates different traffic flows, floating only the TCP queues, looking for more bandwidth while maintaining lower latency (and low queue occupancy) for the other flows. The same consideration described for RSUC1 also holds for RSUA, with just a lower gap which is harder to be noticed.

The extra test RRUL QoS helped us investigate the performance of RSUA very well, which gives us a clear example of packet scheduling coupled with QoS guarantees. Figure 9 shows the download performance of four different TCP market traffic instead of the four BE traffic of RRUL BE. On the one hand, RSUC1 divides the bandwidth almost equally while RSUC2 struggles a little bit more in this task, and this perfectly matches our previous analysis: RSUC1 properly schedules the different traffic sources while RSUC2 does not. On the other hand, RSUA manifests the typical pattern of QoS: we know from the previous analysis that RSUA is able to share the bandwidth between equally important flows, but in this case, it treats the flows differently according to their marks, assigning higher bandwidth to CS5 (real-time) traffic, and reducing the bandwidth for background (non-latency-sensitive) traffic as well. Aggregating all the results in Figure 10, we obtain similar results to Figure 7a; indeed, marking or not marking traffic should not have to impact the overall performance of the aggregated flows. In conclusion, Figure 11 reports the RTT details for the four flows, showing again that RSUA protects the CS5 class flow, penalizing the BK one in terms of latency.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the performance evaluation of the MASA backbone demonstrates its capability to support critical ITS applications with minimal latency, even under congested conditions. The tests, conducted using Flent, reveal that the MASA network can maintain induced latency below 100ms in severe congestion, meeting the stringent requirements for safety-related applications. This performance is attributed to the robust network infrastructure and the strategic partnership between the municipality and the university, which eliminates additional network hops.

The insights gained from this preliminary study confirm that the MASA backbone is well-equipped to handle the demands

of autonomous driving and other ITS services. Future work will focus on expanding the test scenarios and integrating more advanced applications to further validate the network's performance in a real-world setting. This study lays a solid foundation for the continued development and deployment of smart mobility solutions in urban environments.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Høiland-Jørgensen, C. A. Grazia, P. Hurtig, and A. Brunstrom, "Flent: The flexible network tester," *ValueTools 2017*, 2017.
- [2] R. Bolla, R. Bruschi, F. Davoli, and F. Cucchietti, "Traffic management and qos provisioning in isp networks: Challenges and innovations," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 78–84, 2021.
- [3] H. Hlavacs, A. Moldovan, and M. Fiedler, "Quality of service and traffic management in isp networks," *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 845–868, 2017.
- [4] X. Duan, X. Wang, and W. Shi, "Differentiated services for qos provisioning in urban networks," in *Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [5] Z. Zheng, X. Shen, and H. Li, "Controlled congestion points for local traffic management in urban networks," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 1256–1268, 2020.
- [6] X. He, W. Liu, and T. Zhang, "Deep reinforcement learning for routing optimization in mec networks," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 213–227, 2023.
- [7] J. Kua, J. Koh, and W.-S. Ang, "Adaptive queue management for dash video streaming in urban networks," *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 1493–1504, 2020.
- [8] —, "Impact of adaptive queue management on dash-based content delivery," in *Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [9] T. Jiang, H. Zhang, and W. Xu, "Q-fdba: Qoe fairness-driven bandwidth allocation for video streaming," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1471–1483, 2018.
- [10] H. Xue, W. Zhang, and R. Li, "Intelligent content diffusion in smart-router networks for smart cities," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 7769–7779, 2019.
- [11] N. Kumar, S. Singh, and R. Gupta, "Semi-oblivious traffic engineering for smart city networks," in *Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE International Conference on Smart City Innovations (SCI)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [12] C. A. Grazia, N. Patriciello, T. Høiland-Jørgensen, M. Klapez, M. Casoni, and J. Manges-Bafalluy, "Adapting tcp small queues for ieee 802.11 networks," in *2018 IEEE 29th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [13] M. Casoni, C. A. Grazia, and M. Klapez, "Enabling resource pooling in wireless networks through software-defined orchestration," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC)*, May 2016, pp. 730–735.
- [14] —, "A software-defined 5g cellular network with links virtually pooled for public safety operators," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 28, no. 3, p. e3092, 2017, e3092 ett.3092.
- [15] M. Casoni, C. Grazia, and M. Klapez, "An sdn and cps based opportunistic upload splitting for mobile users," in *Proceedings of the EAI International Conference on CYber physiCaL systems, iOt and sensors Networks*, ser. IOT360 Summit '15, 2015.
- [16] "MASA Preliminary Test Repository," UniMoRe, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://netlab.unimore.it/sw/WiMob24.zip>
- [17] S. Ha, I. Rhee, and L. Xu, "Cubic: a new TCP-friendly high-speed TCP variant," *ACM SIGOPS*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 64–74, 2008.
- [18] N. Cardwell, Y. Cheng, C. Stephen Gunn, S. Yeganeh, and V. Jacobson, "BBR: Congestion-based congestion control," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 58–66, 2017.